

NEWSERA Indicators for Communication Strategies of Citizen Science Projects

Description

[NEWSERA](#) project aimed at demonstrating citizen science (CS) as the new paradigm for science communication (scicomm). For this, NEWSERA enrolled 39 CS projects as pilots to co-design, implement and validate communication strategies aimed at quadruple helix agents (citizens and society at large, academia, public sector and policymakers, industry and SMEs) and science and data journalists. This methodology was carried out through co-creation sessions under the #CitSciComm Labs, by the NEWSERA community of practice (CoP), composed by pilots representatives, invited stakeholder representatives, scicomm professionals and NEWSERA team members.

The following document presents a set of indicators (Table 1) for the evaluation of communication strategies specifically aimed at the quadruple helix agents and journalists, by CS projects. These were defined by the NEWSERA Consortium, based on the co-creation work carried out during the development of NEWSERA, as well as on previous work conducted by the CS community in Europe. As explained in Deliverable 2. 2 "Report on indicators for impact assessment of science communication in Citizen Science Projects" ([Giardullo et al. 2021](#)), NEWSERA established a multilevel impact assessment framework, considering impact assessment in three sources: Science Communication Actions (from initial NEWSERA Impact Assessment), the evaluation of Science Communication in different dimensions (from [ACTION Project](#)), and the Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) pillars (from the MoRRI and [Super-MoRRI](#) projects), for the analysis and evaluation of communication tools and strategies co-designed by science communication projects.

Based on this framework model, the NEWSERA Indicators were organised in three key macro-areas, Communication, Participation of quadruple helix stakeholders and Impact, each with three related sub-areas, and specific indicators. In addition, through a process of iterative evaluation, the different indicators have been tested and refined, always in a co-created way together with NEWSERA pilot projects, in a continuous work of mentoring, cooperation and shared learning.

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Table 1. NEWSERA Indicators for Communication Strategies of Citizen Science Projects

Macro-Areas	Sub-areas	Indicators	Type of answer
Communication (definition: The way in which a given citizen science project relates to the various stakeholders: what communication tools and the approaches it uses to share its information, and what role citizen scientists play)	Channels	Does the project have a presence on mass media (e.g. TV, radio, newspapers or magazines)?	TV Radio Podcasting Newspapers Magazines Other
		Does the project have a presence on social media networks?	Twitter Facebook LinkedIn Instagram YouTube TikTok Other
		Does the project include innovative means of science communication and popular media (e.g. art)?	Yes No No, but we want to
		Does the project have direct contact with journalists?	Yes No No, but we want to
	Actions	Does the project have a targeted outreach and communication strategy?	Yes No No, but we want to
		Are citizen scientists involved in communicating, spreading or sharing results?	Never Few times Many times Usually
		How many public meetings/events per year does the project participate and/or organize?	Less than 3 [3-5] [5-10] More than 10

		Does the project use informal and formal communication tools to get connection, upgrade and inform the citizens?	Formal communication only (e.g. web, e-mails, institutional, traditional digital and non-digital media, formal face-to-face or virtual events) Informal communication only (e.g. forums, private emails, whatsapp channels, telegram, etc., informal face-to-face or virtual meetings) Both formal and informal communication
		Does the project have any co-authorship guidelines for the publication of results?	Yes No No, but we want to
	Products¹	Is there an increase in community reach on social media (to specify: twitter, fb, etc.)?	Annual increase % (visits in the specific media)
		Is there an increase in the number of followers on social media (to specify: twitter, fb, etc.)?	Annual increase % (in the specific media)
	Stakeholder engagement (definition: Ability of the citizen science projects to involve, motivate and stimulate participation through specific communication strategies for each stakeholder)	Target audience alignment	Does the project considers diversity in project's public meetings composition in terms of Age range
Does the project considers diversity in project's public meetings composition in terms of Level of education			In general, we do achieve the wide diversity we want to In general, we don't achieve the wide diversity we want to The project is addressed to a very specific educational level
Does the project considers diversity in project's public meetings composition in terms of Gender			In general, we do achieve the wide diversity we want to In general, we don't achieve the wide diversity we want to Other
Does the project considers diversity in project's public meetings composition in terms of quadruple-helix representatives			In general, we do achieve the wide diversity we want to In general, we don't achieve the wide diversity we want to The meetings are addressed to a very specific audience

		Does the project stimulate political and public sector participation (e.g. through participatory meetings, interviews, other means)?	Yes No, we don't seek it No, but we want to
		Does the project stimulate academic research participation (e.g. through data/methodology validation, participatory meetings, interviews, other means)?	Yes No, we don't seek it No, but we want to
		Does the project seek collaboration with science communication professionals?	Yes No No, but we want to
		Has the project elaborated policy briefs or formats (infographics, etc.) directed to policy makers?	Yes No, we don't seek it No, but we want to
		Have you discovered any new stakeholders via any social media listening tool (eg. KAMPAL)?	Yes No No, but we want to
	Level of engagement	What is the general level of engagement of stakeholders in your project?	Passive: stakeholder as receivers of information Active: stakeholder as participants in the communication process (multidirectional communication)
		Are the participation options and the degree of involvement diversified? Which levels can people participate in?	Contributory (provide/collect data) Collaborative (provide/collect data and/or analyse data) Co-created (participate in all or almost all the research cycle)
		Are citizen scientists participating in publications or is their engagement recognized?	Yes, some of them are co-authors Yes, they appear in the acknowledgments (no by name) No
		Is the recognition of citizen scientists being measured by use of advanced tracking citation systems?	Yes No No, but we want to
		What is the ratio of registered users and active users?	Number #
		Are the project objectives and results clearly and transparently communicated?	Yes, always Yes, in general Not as we would like

	Openness	Does the project have a data management plan, IPR strategy and ethical guidelines?	Yes No No, but we want to
		Is the data handling process transparent? (E.g. do citizens know what the data is used for, where the data is stored and shared?)	Yes, always Yes, in general Not as we would like
		Does the project have open interfaces to connect to other systems and platforms?	Yes, always Yes, in general Not as we would like
		Is the generated data shared publicly and under which conditions, e.g. anonymized, metadata, ownership, consent, etc.?	It is not shared so far Always metadata Sometimes metadata Always explicitly under RGPD
		Are data shared disaggregated in terms of sex and gender variables?	Yes No No, but we want to
Impact	Economic	Does the project have any cooperation for exploitation, e.g. with social entrepreneurs?	Yes No, we don't seek it No, but we want to
		Does the project generate any economic impact, e.g. cost reduction, new job creation, new business model, etc.?	Yes No No, but we want to
	Scientific	Does any cross-fertilization of projects take place?	Yes No No, but we want to
		Does the project link to experts from other disciplines?	Yes, because It's a multi or inter or trans disciplinary project Yes, for different reasons No, because we work in a very specific area No, for different reasons No, but we want to
		Does the project collaborate with other initiatives at national or international level to enhance mutual learning and adaptation?	Yes, at both levels Yes, at national level Yes, at international level No No, but we want to

	Political	Does the project have any impact on political decisions?	Yes, intentionally Yes, indirectly Probably Possibly Don't know
		How many activities/reports related to policies has the project achieved?	Yes No Don't know
	Social	Does the project collaborate with local organisations (e.g. in environmental or social fields)?	Yes No No, but we want to
		Did the project contribute to any institutional or structural changes?	Yes No Don't know
		What institutional or structural changes has the project brought about?	Open answer
		Number of schools (number of teachers and students)	Number #
		Have you had any educational materials and resources derived from the project (e.g. MOOCs) being applied?	Yes No

*By “products” we intend a countable communicative outcome that is measured in terms of increased participation (expressed in %) in selected activities.

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